

DEVELOPMENT AND ESTABLISHMENT OF PSYCHOMETRIC PROPERTY OF PATIENCE SCALE IN URDU (PSU)

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DOI:

Keywords:

Patience, Perseverance, Endurance, Behavioral Control, Intolerance.

Article History

Received on 22 March, 2026

Accepted on 06 April, 2026

Published on 08 April, 2026

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Abstract

The present study aimed to construct and validate a Patience scale in Urdu (PSU) which is culturally and linguistically relevant for Pakistani people. The study involved two phases while developing a scale, the first phase dealt with item generation and second phase dealt with Exploratory Factor analysis (EFA). A logical content strategy was used, whereby an initial 50 item pool was generated by the researcher. These items were subjected to qualitative analysis by the expert of subject field. Following a thorough review, 46 items were retained which was further analyzed quantitatively. The scale was administered on a sample of 250 individuals aged 17-50 years (M=25.28, SD=7.51). The sampling adequacy was confirmed using Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure, which yielded a value of .75. Principal Component Analysis with Direct Oblimin rotation showed three factor solution, which was further approved by Scree plot explaining 25.13% of the total variance. The total 33 items were loaded successfully on subscales of PSU meeting the cut-off score of .30 or higher. The three factors were labelled as perseverance/endurance, behavioral control, and intolerance. The overall reliability coefficient of the scale was .77, indicating high internal consistency. Based on these findings, Patience Scale in Urdu has sound psychometric properties considering it a reliable instrument and valid measure of assessing patience within Pakistani context.

Introduction

The construct of patience is gaining importance in psychology since it has become the strongest trait and strength in one's personality. It helps in promoting human's well-being and success. The famous idiom "good things come to those who wait" - means those who are patient and consistent in their moves will receive positive outcomes in the end. According to Harned (1997), some of the religious writers and moral philosophers have emphasized on the importance of patience to get 'good life'.

Patience has attained quite enough importance in the religion Islam and considered it an important aspect of virtue and moral of excellence. In Quranic Verse; "O you who have believed, seek help through patience and prayer. Indeed, Allah is with the patient", (Surah Al-Baqarah (2:153)) - the more human holds the rope of patience and prayers during their trails and difficulties, the more they are strengthening their faith and relationship with Almighty Allah. Likewise, in another Quranic verse; "Indeed, the patient will be given their reward without measure." Surah Az-Zumar (39:10). Allah has promised his people for rewarding them with bounty if they show patience when facing some life challenges.

The word patience has been derived from Latin word 'pati' which means to suffer, to endure and to bear, and the French word 'patient' means 'enduring without complaint.' Patience is a virtue which is the acceptance of delay, difficulty and frustration. Saint Augustine has defined patience as; "Patience is the companion of wisdom." Michelangelo defined it as; "Genius is eternal patience." It means that the concept of patience has been recognized as a human strength and virtue of moral excellence.

According to Houlberg and Schnitker (2019), patience refers to the endurance of difficult time, even if it's within the relationships or when facing daily life challenges. Patience demands acceptance of difficulty, delay or setbacks through the strength and staying firm and persistent in moves. This virtue has gained high importance due to its impact on well-being of humans. Some researches on patience have suggested that it promotes not only healthy physical wellbeing, but emotional, mental and social well being as well. Some of the participants in research who have claimed to be patient have rated themselves being mindful, grateful, strong sense of connectivity to mankind and universe, and possessing sense of fulfillment.

Frasyniuk and Svider (2020), have explained the philosophical examination of patience in four contexts, which are; as an attribute of the material and ideal world (Aristotle), a virtue related

to the sufferings and pleasure (Aristotle & Tertullian etc.), a subjective need for suffering (Kant) and a foundation to human life (Schopenhauer). Early philosophers like Socrates or Plato has defined patience as valuable quality and fundamental virtue of life. Some of the key features of patience includes, expectation, endurance, obedience, misery, self-control, exposure, leniency and perseverance.

The operational definition of patience is defined as consisting of “both behavioral (i.e., waiting) and emotional (i.e., low arousal positive affect and notable absence of high arousal negative affect) components. To elaborate this definition further, intense negative affect like fear, anxiety or anger, inhibit patience more than some low-arousal negative affect like disappointment, sadness or melancholy. Likewise, low-arousal positive affect like contentment, gratitude or admiration will facilitate patience as compared to high arousal-positive affect like excitement, anticipation or enthusiasm. (Schnitker, 2012).

The study by Worthen (2018) demonstrates the importance of patience and highlights its importance in five domains which are; confidence and control, distress tolerance, relationships improvement, character development and spiritual maturation. According to Schnitker (2012), patience plays a significant role in pursuing a goal. She concludes that patience plays an important role in maintaining the wellbeing of an individual who is suffering through difficulty or tough time.

Some researchers have studied about the construct of hope which elicits positive emotions after attaining a goal, especially after overcoming obstacles. (Snyder, Rand, & Sigmon, 2005, p. 258). Patience requires persistence to overcome obstacles or adversity when one is facing. It boosts the stamina to acquire the goals and leads to satisfaction also. Some studies have provided patience correlation with satisfaction with life, hope and good self-esteem. It also contributes towards the improved sense of wellbeing. (Schnitker, 2012; Schnitker & Emmons, 2007).

The *Regulatory focus theory* (Higgins, 1997), signifies the role of patience in control efforts. The theory describes the two approaches towards attainment of goal. The first one is pointing at growth and aspirations (Promotion Focused) and the second one indicates towards safety and responsibility (Prevention focused). The promotion approach focuses on adding gains while limiting non-gains, which leads towards goal acquirement and development. On the other hand, prevention approach focuses on one’s safety, and security. It also protects

things one has and preventing losing things which are important. Both are focused on eagerly pursuing gains and vigilantly avoiding losses. An example would be goal of employment which requires patience in sustaining efforts to search for it, and then securing it. It also plays a role in maintaining the wellbeing if one is not getting an employment leading to distress. Patience filters the negative affect and helps in sustaining efforts, two essential requirements for maintaining hope. (Schnitker & Emmons, 2007).

According to Dudley (2003), patience can be assessed through cognitive reactions as well as affective responses. Some of the positive and negative feelings that are experienced from the past in the face of waiting and compelling circumstances of the individual have an important place in the affective evaluation of patience. Bülbül and Arslan (2017), studied the level of patience in terms of self-compassion, self-determinism and personality traits. The findings have shown a significant positive correlation between patience and self-compassion across all dimension. Also, the positive correlation between patience and the self-contact which is the sub dimension of self-determinism reflects emotional awareness. They also assessed the patience level in personality traits while using the big five dimensions of personality. Where the patience is positively correlated with agreeableness, conscientiousness and openness to experience, but it is negatively correlated with neuroticism and extraversion with little or no relationship. To conclude the study, the individuals with greater self-compassion and emotional awareness tend to be more patience in comparison to those suffering from neurotic tendencies.

Patience is a moral virtue and has therapeutic quality. In Quran, patience is mentioned more than hundred times, primarily focusing on it as self-restraint, emotional control, and tolerating the hardships. It can be classified into several forms like patience during worship, enduring misfortunes, resisting sinful desires, and staying patient with others wrongdoings. Some of the mental health problems like anxiety, depressions, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and behavioral disorders have their roots in lack of self-control and emotional disbalance. So, the patience plays an important role in learning calmness when anxious, managing emotions well and to strengthen spiritual wellbeing of an individual. (Alfain, Soleh, & Yamani, 2023).

The present study is addressing the knowledge gap by developing and establishing the psychometric properties of an indigenous Patience Scale in Urdu (PSU), relevant to the culture

and norm, and providing a valid and reliable tool for assessing patience, an important psychological aspect among Pakistani population.

Rationale

Patience is an important psychological trait which has profound influence on the human wellbeing and their behavior. Its importance is highlighted in three monotheistic religions, that is, Islam, Christianity and Judaism (Wainwright, 2018). As it is the fundamental characteristic of human beings when they encounter the difficult situations. Likewise, waiting is one form of patience which is unavoidable part of life. At times, human beings have to rely on patience to tolerate disappointments and sustain wellbeing in the most crucial or frustrating circumstances. This not only helps in making the better decisions but taking good control over the self from facing further troubles.

According to DeLongis, Coyne, et.al. 1982, there is high risk for the physical as well as mental wellbeing to be affected by the frustrations due to daily nuisance in surrounding. As a result impatience causing stress, frustration and anxiety affecting mental health. Schnitker and Emmons, (2007) have studied that the patience is associated with the subjective wellbeing, positive coping and struggles of an individual.

As highlighted above, patience is an important characteristic of a personality which needs to be studied in specific culture. Although there have been various scales developed for measuring patience, like, Schnitker (2012) scale for US population, comprised of three factor patience questionnaires; included interpersonal patience, life hardship patience and daily hassles patience as factors. Khormaei et.al. (2014) has developed a scale of patience (ساخت و بررسی ویژگیهای روان سنجی مقیاس صبر) for an Iranian sample, which has five factors based on significance, tolerance, persistence, satisfaction and delay. Another scale for patience is developed by Deng and Li (2016), constructed and validated the Buddhist Patience Scale which has three factors, to voluntarily endure suffering, to respond with retaliation towards damaged suffering and patience realized through learning the factor of existence.

The three above mentioned scales are linguistically and culturally validated according to their norms. These scales are based on Western constructs, or developed for Iranian population, which is in Persian language which makes it difficult to apply on Pakistani population due to language barrier or not clearly defined according to our sociocultural context.

Therefore, the need is to develop an indigenous scale which is culturally, religiously and linguistically valid and applicable on respective population.

The present study highlights the importance of developing and constructing a scale in Urdu which is the national language of Pakistan. Pakistan is an ideological state where the predominant religion is Islam and the native language is Urdu. It is necessary to develop a psychological assessment tool on patience that can reflect our basic foundations, covers Islamic principles, designed in Urdu language for ensuring cultural relevance, and its applicability within the local population.

Objectives

- 1- The primary purpose of this research study is to develop a reliable measuring tool for Patience in Urdu language, which is readable, comprehensible and widely spoken language in Pakistan.
- 2- To establish the psychometric properties of the Patience scale in Urdu, to validate it and use it for drawing inferences.
- 3- To identify the factor structure of the scale in order to define the sub dimensions and attain better understanding of the concept of Patience among Pakistani population.

Method

The present study was aiming to develop a culturally and linguistically relevant indigenous scale, the construction of this scale has been gone through two study methods. The first phase was based on Item Generation and Qualitative item analysis and the second phase covers the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA).

Phase 1 – Item Generation

An initial item pool consisted of 50 items which was further administered to qualitative analysis by an expert in the field. Creating items took considerable time to ensure that it was accurately covering the intended construct being measured. All items were created in five-point Likert format. After the review by an expert, items were deduced to 46.

Phase 2 – Exploratory Factor Analysis

The study went through an experimental try out stage, where exploratory factor analysis was applied on the items of Patience Scale in Urdu. The scale was applied on 250 sample through convenience sampling method. The sample varied in age, gender, and educational background and socioeconomic status.

Sample

In this study, the participants were selected based on convenience sampling from Department of Psychology, University of Peshawar, University of Science and Technology Bannu, University of Engineering Peshawar, and random general population. The total sample size was 250 ($M=118.24$, $SD=13.99$) where 125 males and 125 females were taken as participants. The age range was from 17 to 50 years. There were variations in the education level of participants, minimum pursuing at least intermediate degree.

Instrument

Demographic Sheet

The participants were asked to add their individual identification before responding to items. The information was based on participant's Name, age, gender, education, religion and language.

Patience Scale in Urdu (PSU)

The first step in creating a scale was focused on logical content approach, where statements of Patience Scale in Urdu (PSU) were based on deductive approach. This method involved writing items which were logically and conceptually relevant to the construct of patience being measured. The operational definition of patience is "the propensity to wait calmly in the face of frustration, adversity or suffering." (Schnitker, 2012).

The scale was designed in five-point Likert format, which included 'Completely Wrong', 'Wrong', 'Not Sure', 'Right', 'Completely Right'. While constructing a scale, negative statements were also added to minimize the chances of fake responses or ruling out the fake responses along reducing the tendency to mark agree for most of the statements. Afterwards, reverse scoring of such statements was operated on SPSS version 27. The reverse scored items included; Item No. 5, 6, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, and 46.

Procedure

The participants required for this research study were approached at their educational institute. They were given a brief gist of the study, its purpose and informed consent was taken before they would fill the questionnaires. They were asked for their willingness to volunteer themselves for the study. Those who agreed were given the Patience scale in Urdu. Participants were instructed to read and answer each question carefully without missing any item. In order to avoid bias responses due to social desirability, the questionnaire given to them was untitled

and their responses were kept completely anonymous. The test constructor was available in the moment of administering it to help participants in case they might face some confusion or difficulty while marking the items on questionnaire. Some participants were handed over the questionnaire to fill them at their convenient time and returned them the following day. Out of 345 questionnaires distributed, 250 were selected because of the accuracy of information provided and rest were discarded due to incomplete information or faked responses. All those forms which had complete information were used for data analysis, which was conducted while using SPSS version 27. Participants were thanked in the end for taking their time out for filling the questionnaires.

Results

Table 1: *KMO and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity of Sampling Adequacy for PSU*

KMO	Bartlett's Test	Df	P
.75	1820.2	561	.00

Note. PSU=Patience Scale in Urdu

The findings in Table 1 indicates that Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant. The Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was .74, which has supported the use of Factor Analysis.

Table 2: *Eigen Values and Percentages of Variances of PSU*

Factors	Eigen Value	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	6.36	13.83	13.83
2	2.94	6.39	20.22
3	2.25	4.90	25.13

Note. PSU= Patience Scale in Urdu

The results in Table 2 shows the Eigen values, Percentage of Variance and Cumulative Percentage of three factors. The first factor explained 13.83% of the variance, the second factor explained 6.39% of the variance and the third factor explained 4.90% of the variance. Overall the three factors have explained 25.13% of the total variance.

Figure 1: Scree Plot of Patience Scale in Urdu

Figure shows that three factors appear to be above the point of inflection, suggesting a three factor solution of the scale.

Table 3: Factor Loadings of Patience Scale in Urdu (PSU) with Direct Oblimin Rotation

PSU Items	Factor Loadings		
	1	2	3
Factor 1: Perseverance			
4.Mujh par jab koi musibat aan parti hai tou sabar se kaam leti/leta hun.	.35	.25	.17
5.Mai chizo ka tariqa istemal parhay baghair he kaam shuru kr deti/deta hun. R	.51	-.24	.19
9.Mai jab zindagi se mayoos ho jati/jata hun tou Allah se madad mangti/mangta hun.	.38	-.25	-.036
11.Mujhy sakht napasand hai k mujhy kisi kaam ki zimdari sonpi jaye. R	.34	.01	.23
12.Mai musibat ky waqt Allah se gila shikwa karti/karta hun. R	.35	-.08	.18
14.Jaldbazi ki bajaye mai apna kaam aram se karti/karta hun.	.37	-.03	.13
28.Mai Apnay walidain ki naseehaton ko ghor se sunti/sunta hun.	.59	.01	-.17
31.Mai apna kaam khush asloobi se karti karta hun.	.60	.14	-.07

32. Meri koshish hoti hai ky mai apna sara kaam waqt pr kiya karun.	.70	.07	-.07
39. Mai apnay jazbat pr qabu rakh sakta/sakti hun.	.46	.11	.12
40. Mai baat naram lehjay mai karna pasand karta/karti hun.	.43	.17	-.07
41. Mai gham ky moqay pr sabar se kaam leti/leta hun.	.52	.09	.00
42. Mai dusro ki baat tahamul se sunta/sunti hun.	.58	.10	-.00
45. Mai sabit qadmi se masail ka hal talash karny ki koshish karta/karti hun.	.57	.16	-.14

Factor 2: Behavioural control

3. Jab koi mujh par ghusa karay tou mai agay se chup ho jati hun/jata hun.	-.07	.60	.18
8. Mujhy apnay ghusay pr qabu rakhna ata hai.	.16	.50	.25
19. Kisi kimti chiz ky gum ho janay pr mai sabar se kaam leti/leta hun.	.08	.41	.15
27. Behas ky doran mai aksar khamoshi ikhtiyar karti/karta hun.	.19	.41	-.12
30. Jab koi mera mazak urata hai tou mai tahamul se kaam leti leta hun.	.11	.59	.02
33. Mai logo ky ghusay pr koi rade.amal ikhtiyar nahi karta/karti.	.01	.54	-.20
34. Mai apnay khwahishat pr dusro ki khwahishat ko foqiyat deta/deti hun.	.08	.33	-.16
35. Agar koi meray sath ziyadti karay tou mai kisi kisam ky rade-amal ka izhar nahi karta/karti.	-.21	.64	-.08
37. Mujhay jaldi ghusa nahi ata.	.07	.39	.01

Factor 3: Intolerance

6. Mujhy jaldi jaldi kam khatam karna pasand hai. R	-.02	-.04	.30
10. Mai mushkil halaat mai jald ghabra jati/jata hun. R	.16	-.00	.42
16. Mujhay inteazar karna bilkul pasand nahi. R	.07	.16	.41
18. Bachon ky tang karnay par mai ghusa ho jati jata hun. R	-.20	-.02	.44
21. Bhook ki halat mai khanay ka inteazar karnay se mujhay shadeed koft hoti hai. R	.15	.04	.36
22. Agar meray sath koi bura karay tou mai hargiz maaf nahi karti/karta hun. R	.25	-.05	.45

23. Mujhay apnay kaam mai ghiaro ki mudakhlat nagawar guzarti hai. R	-.19	-.04	.38
24. Mujhay choto ka har baat mai bolna bardasht nahi hota. R	-.07	.12	.45
25. Mujhay mamuli si bhi jismani takleef bardash nahi. R	.24	-.15	.44
46. Agar koi hamary sath bura karay tou uskay sath bhi bura karna chahye. R	.27	.05	.36

Note. N=250. Extraction method was Principal Component Analysis with Direct Oblimin in Rotation. Item loadings $\geq .30$ presented in bold, and reverse-coded items are represented with R. The findings in Table 5 indicates the factor loadings of Patience Scale in Urdu (PSU) on three factors. Factor 1 included 14 items (4,5,9,11,12,14,28,31,32,39,40,41,42,45) with factor loadings ranging from .34 to .70. Factor 2 included 9 items (3,8,19,27,30,33,34,35,37) with factor loadings ranging from .33 to .64. Factor 3 comprised of 10 items (6,10,16,18,21,22,23,24,25,46) with factor loadings in the range of .30 to .45.

Table 4: *Alpha Reliability of PSU and its Subscales*

Scales	No. of items	Mean	SD	Range	Alpha Coefficient
PSU	33	116.28	13.93	43 - 153	.77
Perseverance	14	55.56	7.26	18 - 60	.77
Behavioral Control	9	29.76	6.04	11 - 45	.69
Intolerance	10	30.96	6.46	14 - 60	.58

Note. PSU = Patience Scale in Urdu

The Table 4 shows that PSU scale demonstrated high reliability ($\alpha = .77$) of the total scale. Whereas, its sub-dimensions, Perseverance/Endurance subscale also showed high reliability ($\alpha = .77$), Behavioral Control showed moderate reliability ($\alpha = .69$) and Intolerance demonstrated acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .58$).

Discussion

The present study aimed at creating an indigenous scale on Patience, which should be culturally and linguistically relevant to the culture of Pakistan. The construct of Patience has been studied and measured via Western and Buddhist culture as well as one scale is available for Iranian population. These scales have either a separate culture and/or different language (e.g., in Persian language) which makes it hard to apply these scales here. To address this gap, a scale was developed using logical content approach while defining comprehensively the construct of Patience. Overall, literature was reviewed to understand the constructs related to patience which helped in proceeding to item generation phase. Initially 50 items were generated with reference of Pakistani population, including their culture and norms. The study was divided into two phases i.e. Item generation phase and Exploratory Factor Analysis. In the first phase, the initial pool was examined by the subject expert for its linguistic clarity, meaning and relevance to the culture. Based on the judgement of an expert, some items were removed due to its poor cohesion of words and concepts, some were changed into appropriate wording or redefined. Thus, 46 items in total were retained for the further process or analysis.

After the qualitative item analysis, the retained items were proceeded to quantitative item analysis via factor analysis in order to determine the factorial validity of the instrument. The sample adequacy was assessed using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure, which produced a value of .74, thereby indicating good suitability for factor analysis (as shown in Table 1). Bartlett's test of sphericity was also highly significant ($df=561$, $\chi^2=1820.2$, $p=.000$), suggesting that factor analysis could be performed on the data.

Exploratory Factor Analysis was applied on the remaining 46 items after qualitative item analysis using Principal Component Analysis with Direct Oblimin as rotation method to finalize the factor structure of the scale. Eigen value greater than 1 was selected as a criterion to determine number of factors in the scale, while considering the cut-off score .30 or above for the items to be retained within its respective factor. Scree plot (Figure 1) also demonstrated a three-factor structure, therefore a subsequent analysis of fixed value to three factors was calculated. Those items meeting the threshold value of .30 or above were retained in the scale (3,4,5,6,8,9,10,11,12,14,16,18,19,21,22,23,24,25,27,28,30,31,32,33,34,35,37,39,40,41,42,45, & 46) and the items below .30 were excluded from the scale (1, 2, 7, 13, 15, 17, 20, 26, 29, 36, 38, 43, & 44) due to lack of its logical content or relevance., being double barreled, cross

loaded or below the cut-off point. Consequently, thirty-three (33) items fulfilled the criteria were retained in the scale, yielding three factor solution. The three dimensions combined together explains 25.135% of the total variance (see Table 2). The first factor has an Eigen value of 6.36, explaining 13.83% of the variance, the second factor yielded Eigen value 2.94 that accounts for 6.39% of the variance. While, the third factor explained 4.90% of the variance with an Eigen value of 2.25. As shown in Table 5, the items were significantly loaded on three factors.

Each of the item was then thoroughly reviewed to name the sub-factor of Patience Scale in Urdu with appropriate labels measuring that subdimension. *Perseverance*, *Behavioral Control* and *Intolerance* were the names assigned to the three factors (see Table 3 and 4) of Patience Scale in Urdu (PSU). The first factor was labelled as *Perseverance*, consisted of 14 items. It refers to the items that assess one's persistent commitment while staying patient in challenging situations. It included item numbers 4, 5, 9, 11, 12, 14, 28, 31, 32, 39, 40, 41, 42, 45 with factor loadings ranging from .34 to .70. The second factor was named as *Behavioral Control* included 9 items. This factor primarily reflects individual's capacity to resist certain immediate actions that may lead to undesirable outcomes later on. It is comprised of item numbers 3, 8, 19, 27, 30, 33, 34, 35, 37 with factor loadings ranging from .33 to .64. Whereas, the third factor was titled as *Intolerance*. It assesses an individual level of impatience at the time of frustration or delay or any other challenging situation. This factor has 10 items, which are 6, 10, 16, 18, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 46 with factor loadings in the range of .30 to .45.

The three dimensions of PSU scale including Perseverance, behavioral control and intolerance has immense importance in our culture. It is pertinent to connect the three aspects of Patience Scale in Urdu with its eventual outcomes on our society. Perseverance reflects our societal aspects like hard work, resilience and commitment. The other aspect of behavioural control represents social order and respect for norms. It ensures discipline, patience and responsibility. Lastly, the aspect of intolerance leads to conflict, aggression and poor decision-making. Giving the key aspect how to manage it once assessed. Overall, the three dimensions together shapes individual character and personality aspects. Thus, high perseverance, strong behavioural control and low intolerance will lead to more stable out comes or stable personality, bringing harmony in our society.

Following the process of finalizing the factor structure and factors labelling, Cronbach Alpha coefficient was calculated for the PSU scale along its sub-dimensions to assess the internal consistency of the scale (see Table 4). The reliability analysis on the retained items of Patience Scale in Urdu was calculated and it was .77 which showed that the scale was highly reliable. Its sub-dimensions, Perseverance has high reliability ($\alpha = .77$), Behavioral Control showed moderate reliability ($\alpha = .69$) and Intolerance demonstrated acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .58$)

As the present study is about constructing and validating a patience scale which is a multidimensional psychological construct comprising three interrelated dimensions: perseverance, behavioral control and intolerance, with high reliability. Therefore, within Pakistani cultural context, patience represents not only perseverance in times of challenges but also emotional and behavioral control during frustrating situations. Intolerance also assesses one's reduced tolerance towards delay in progress or adversity. These three dimensions, all together, provides a comprehensive framework for understanding patience, giving personal insight and meaning of life approaches.

Conclusion

The present study developed and constructed a valid and reliable tool about patience in Urdu language, which is the national language of Pakistan. It has highlighted patience as a multidimensional construct with promising psychometric properties, with a high reliability of .77. The three dimensions i.e. perseverance and endurance, behavioral control and intolerance, makes the patience scale more cohesive, meaningful and measurable construct. The developed scale provides a reliable and culturally relevant tool to assess patience, highlighting its role in clinical settings, educational environment, interpersonal harmony and workplace situations. It helps in emotional regulation and academic achievements. It helps in psychological assessment and offer a foundation for future research studies and interventions fostering patience in Pakistan.

Implications

The present study has several important implications in various settings, including clinical setups, educational environment, workplace performance and interpersonal relationships. In clinical setting, this tool can be helpful in assessing tolerance level of patients related to their diseases and the process of treatment given. Also it helps in judging the patience level of clinicians in facilitating their patients with fine care, detail workup and tailoring treatment with

mutual collaboration. In educational setting, it helps in learning, motivation and academic tasks with dedication and persistence. In work place, patience promotes logical decision-making, adaptability and managing stress related to work pressure and burnouts. Patience helps in improving interpersonal relationships while tolerating differences and delays, reduces conflicts while promoting communication patiently, incorporating empathy and support relationships.

Limitations and Suggestions

The present study has developed the Patience scale in Urdu which is a valid and reliable measure of construct, there are some limitations that needs to be addressed.

- 1- The sample has majority of the students which may compromise the generalizability of this scale. It has limited diversity of participants which limits its generalizability on other population. Therefore, it is recommended for the future test developers to count in participants from different backgrounds or socioeconomic groups to gain better understanding of people opinions and attitudes.
- 2- The sample is collected through convenience sampling method, which does not cover the broader population. This is again compromising its generalizability. The future test developers should take its account and should use probability sampling method.
- 3- Since this scale has three factor-structure, i.e. perseverance, behavioral control and intolerance, there might be some other relevant factors remained unmeasured. Therefore, the future test developer must explore some other dimensions of patience to enhance its comprehensiveness and applicability.
- 4- Confirmatory factor analysis was not applied on the present study. Thus, the future test developers should make use of it while using well developed software's.

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APPENDIX

بنیادی معلومات

نام: _____ تعلیم: _____

جنس: _____ عمر: _____

ہدایات: یہ سوالنامہ انسانی طبیعت کو جانچنے کیلئے بنایا گیا ہے۔ آپ سے گزارش ہے کہ تمام سوالات کو غور سے پڑھیں اور ہر سوال کے آگے دیئے گئے جوابات میں سے ایسے جواب پر صحیح کا نشان لگائیں جو آپ کی طبیعت کے مطابق ہو۔

بالکل غلط	غلط	پتہ نہیں	درست	بالکل درست	
					1 جب کوئی مجھ پر غصہ کرے تو میں آگے سے چپ ہو جاتی / جاتا ہوں۔
					2 مجھ پر جب کوئی مصیبت آن پڑتی ہے تو صبر سے کام لیتی / لیتا ہوں۔
					3 میں چیزوں کا طریقہ استعمال پڑھے بغیر ہی کام شروع کر دیتا / دیتی ہوں۔
					4 مجھے جلدی جلدی کام ختم کرنا پسند ہے۔
					5 مجھے اپنے غصے پر قابو رکھنا آتا ہے۔
					6 میں جب زندگی سے مایوس ہو جاتی / جاتا ہوں تو اللہ تعالیٰ سے مدد مانگتی / مانگتا ہوں۔
					7 میں مشکل حالات میں جلد گھبرا جاتی / جاتا ہوں۔
					8 مجھے سخت نا پسند ہے کہ مجھے کسی کام کی ذمہ داری سونپی جائے۔
					9 میں مصیبت کے وقت اللہ تعالیٰ سے گلہ شکوہ کرتی / کرتا ہوں۔
					10 جلدی بازی کی بجائے میں اپنا کام آرام سے کرتی / کرتا ہوں۔
					11 مجھے انتظار کرنا بالکل پسند نہیں۔
					12 بچوں کے تنگ کرنے پر میں غصہ ہو جاتی / جاتا ہوں۔
					13 کسی قیمتی چیز کے گم ہو جانے پر میں صبر سے کام لیتی / لیتا ہوں۔

				74	بھوک کی حالت میں کھانے کا انتظار کرنے سے مجھے شدید کوفت ہوتی ہے۔
				75	اگر میرے ساتھ کوئی برا کرے تو میں برگز معاف نہیں کرتی / کرتا۔
				76	مجھے اپنے کام میں غیروں کی مداخلت ناگوار گزرتی ہے۔
				77	مجھے چھوٹوں کا ہر بات میں بولنا برداشت نہیں ہوتا۔
				78	مجھے معمولی سی بھی جسمانی تکلیف برداشت نہیں۔
				79	بحث کے دوران میں اکثر خاموشی اختیار کرتی / کرتا ہوں۔
				20	میں اپنے والدین کی نصیحتوں کو غور سے سنتی / سنتا ہوں۔
				21	جب کوئی میرا مذاق اڑاتا ہے تو میں تحمل سے کام لیتی / لیتا ہوں۔
				22	میں اپنا کام خوش اسلوبی سے کرتی / کرتا ہوں۔
				23	میری کوشش ہوتی ہے کہ میں اپنا سارا کام وقت پر کیا کروں۔
				24	میں لوگوں کے غصے پر کوئی رد عمل اختیار نہیں کرتا / کرتی۔
				25	میں اپنی خواہشات پر دوسروں کی خواہشات کو فوقیت دیتا / دیتی ہوں۔
				26	اگر کوئی میرے ساتھ زیادتی کرے تو میں کسی قسم کے رد عمل کا اظہار نہیں کرتا / کرتی۔
				27	مجھے جلدی غصہ نہیں آتا۔
				28	میں اپنے جذبات پر قابو رکھ سکتی ہوں / سکتا ہوں۔
				29	میں بات نرم لہجے میں کرنا پسند کرتا / کرتی ہوں۔
				30	میں غم کے موقعے پر صبر سے کام لیتی / لیتا ہوں۔
				31	میں دوسروں کی بات تحمل سے سنتا / سنتی ہوں۔
				32	میں ثابت قدمی سے مسائل کا حل تلاش کرنے کی کوشش کرتا / کرتی ہوں۔
				33	اگر کوئی ہمارے ساتھ برا کرے تو اس کے ساتھ بھی برا کرنا چاہئے۔

- 2,3,6,8,9,10,20,22,23,28,29,30,31,32 (Perseverance) تحمل	I
(Behavioral Control) 1,5,13,19,21,24,25,26,27 برداشت-	II
(Intolerance) 4,7,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,33 بے صبری-	III
<i>Reverse Coded Items</i>	
4,7,8,9,11,12,14,15,16,17,18,33	

Note: It's an open access scale. No permission is required for the future use of this scale. The authors should be properly cited and included in the reference list.